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Performance evaluation of an inter-specific hybrid Fremont mandarin on different rootstocks under hot arid environment

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Performance of an interspecific hybrid Fremont mandarin was assessed on different rootstocks in the hot arid regions of India as a potential scion species to expand citrus fruits availability in the arid region. Fremont scion attained superior growth and yield characteristics on Karna khatta rootstock by displaying maximum plant canopy parameters followed by on Rough lemon rootstock. However, the Pectinifera followed by Troyer citrange resulted dwarfness of scion. The scion-rootstock compatibility indicators such as scion rootstock ratio, stionic difference and TCSA which were maximum in favor of Fremont/Pectinifera combination, confirming the inhibited tree growth on Pectinifera rootstock was ascertained by intrinsic feature of rootstock rather than incompatibility reaction. Furthermore, Karna khatta rootstock resulted maximum fruit yield and its related traits followed by Rough lemon and Pectinifera rootstocks. The Pectinifera rootstock resulted almost similar response to all fruit physical attributes i.e., fruit weight, fruit diameter, fruit index and fruiting density, except fruit number. The fruit maturity of Fremont was obtained earliest on Pectinifera, while it was most delayed on Karna khatta and Rough lemon rootstocks. Fruit quality parameters on Pectinifera rootstock was superior to those of common rootstock species (Karna khatta or Rough lemon) for fruit juice content as well as its nutritional constituents like TSS, ascorbic acid, pH, total sugar, organoleptic taste, ripening index, and lower content of acidity, and rind thickness. The total AAE, total flavonoids, total phenol contents were also apparently higher than those obtained on other rootstocks, except Troyer citrange. Overall, Fremont mandarin can be considered a promising scion in arid regions to extend period of harvest of superior quality fruits, especially on dwarfing Pectinifera rootstock. It would be further ease harvesting operation vis-a-vis possible attainment of better micro-climate due to small tree stature and high-density plantation.

Keywords: Citrus, arid region, rootstock, dwarfing, fruit quality, compatibility index.

